

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

SYNTHESIS OF 1-SUBSTITUTED-2-THIO-4-AMINO-6-ETHYLFORMAMIDINO,1,3,5-TRIAZINES

D. T. Tayade* S. P. Ingole

Department of Chemistry, Government Vidarbha Institute of Science and Humanities, Amravati 444606.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 15/02/2018

Available online

31/03/2018

Keywords

Ethanolic,

Elemental Analysis.

ABSTRACT

Recently in this laboratory 1-substituted-2-thio-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino 1,3,5-triazines (XIIIa-r) were synthesised by isomerisation of 2-substituted imino-4-amino-6-formamidino-1,3,5-thiadiazines (XIIa-r) successfully by refluxing with 10% aqueous ethanolic sodium bicarbonate medium. The structure of all the synthesized compounds was justified on the basis of chemical characteristics, elemental analysis and spectral studies.

Corresponding author

D. T. Tayade

Department of Chemistry,

Government Vidarbha Institute of Science and Humanities,

Amravati 444606.

skdtayade@gmail.com, anilsphd@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **D. T. Tayade et al.** Synthesis of 1-Substituted-2-Thio-4-Amino-6-Ethylformamidino,1,3,5-Triazines. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(03).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

The 1,3,5-triazine nucleus containing compounds having huge importance in human life due to their varieties of applications in medicinal, industrial pharmaceutical and agricultural fields¹⁻⁶. These 1,3,5-triazines have their own identity and importance in medicinal⁷, pharmaceutical⁸, agricultural⁹ and industrial¹⁰ fields few of them possesses antidiabetic¹¹⁻¹², anti-tumor¹³⁻¹⁶, anti-inflammatory¹⁷, anti-depressant¹⁸, hypoglycaemic¹⁹ activities. They are also used as herbicidal²⁰⁻²⁶, fungicidal²⁷⁻²⁹, insecticidal³⁰, anti-corrosive³¹, antimicrobial³² and anti-convulsant³³ properties. Hence it was thought interesting to carry out the isomerisation of 2-substitutedguanidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazines (XIIa-r) into 1-substituted-2-substitutedguanidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazines (XIIIa-r) in the presence of 10% ethanolic sodium bicarbonate medium. The tentative reaction for the formation of product is depicted below (Scheme-I).

Scheme-I.

General remarks

All reagents were purchased from commercial suppliers and used without further purification. Dry methanol and diethyl ether were purchased from Aldrich and were used as such. All reactions were run in oven-dried round bottom flask or vial containing a teflon-coated stir bar and sealed with septum. Analytical thin layer chromatography was carried out on silica pre-coated glass plates (Silica gel 60 F254, 0.25 mm thickness) and visualized with UV light at 254 nm. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400-MHz Ultrashield Advance II 400 model (400 and 100 MHz, respectively) at ambient temperature with CDCl₃ or DMSO-d₆ as solvents. Data for ¹H are recorded as follows: δ chemical shift (ppm), multiplicity (s, singlet; d, doublet; dd, double doublet; t, triplet; q, quartet; m, multiplet), coupling constant (Hz), integration. Spectra were referenced internally to the residual proton resonance in CDCl₃ (δ 7.26 ppm), DMSO-d₆ (δ 2.50 ppm) or with tetramethylsilane (TMS, δ 0.00 ppm) as the internal standard. Chemical shifts (δ) were reported as part per million (ppm) in δ scale downfield from TMS.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

General procedure for the Synthesis of 1-ethyl-2-formamidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine (XIIIa)

2-Ethylimino-4-amino-6-formamidino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (XIIa) was suspended in 10% ethanolic sodium bicarbonate solution and refluxed for half an hour on water bath. During heating the reactant went into the solvent. After distillation of excess solvent milky white crystals were isolated and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid to obtain (XIIIa), Yield 78%, m.p. 185^oC.

Properties of [XIIIa]

It is brown colour crystalline solid having melting point 185^oC. It gave positive test for nitrogen and sulphur. It was desulphurized by alkaline plumbite solution which clearly indicate the presence of C=S group. It was soluble in water, ethanol, DMSO-d₆ while insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, benzene, petroleum ether. It formed picrate having melting point 209^oC. Elemental analysis: [C: 61.20% (found), 62.10% (calculated)], [H: 03.51% (found), 04.99 % (calculated)], [N: 18.11% (found), 18.11 % (calculated)], [S: 10.84% (found), 11.82 % (calculated)]. IR Spectrum: The IR spectrum was carried out in KBr-pellets The important absorptions are correlated as (cm⁻¹) 3180.62 N-H stretching, 2895.15 C-H stretching, 1726.89 N=C-N stretching, 1514.12 N-C=S stretching, 1288.45 C-N stretching, 1010.70 C=S stretching. NMR Spectrum: The NMR spectrum was carried out in DMSO-d₆ and CDCl₃ This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals due to Ar-H protons at δ 8.4227-6.9756 ppm, -NH proton at δ 3.6302-3.0104 ppm, -CH₃ protons at δ 1.3791-1.3437 ppm.

Similarly, 2-phenylimino-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine (XIIb), 2-methylimino-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine (XIIc), 2-p-chlorophenylimino-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-thiadiazine(XIId), 2-otolylimino-4-amino-6-phenylformamidino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (XIIe), 2-m-tolylimino-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (XIIIf) and 2-p-tolylimino-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (XIIg) were isomerised by 10% aqueous ethanol to isolate 1-phenyl-2-thio-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-triazine (XIIIb), 1-methyl-2-thio-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-triazine (XIIIc), 1-p-chlorophenyl-2-thio-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-triazine (XIIIId), 1-o-tolyl-2-thio-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-triazine(XIIIe), 1-m-tolyl-2-thio-4-amino-6-phenylformamidino -1,3,5-triazine (XIIIIf), 1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino-1,3,5-triazine (XIIIg) and enlisted in Table- VI-1.

Table-VI-1.

Sr. No.	1-substituted-2-thio-4-amino-6-ethylformamidino1,3,5-triazines	Yield %	M. P.
1.	1-methyl-2-formamidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine	94	272
2.	1-methyl-2-formamidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine	94	272
3.	1-p-chlorophenyl-2-formamidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine	92	275
4.	1-o-tolyl-2-formamidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine	98	222
5.	1-m-tolyl-2-formamidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine	94	247
6.	1-p-tolyl-2-formamidino-4-amino-6-thio-1,3,5-triazine	94	268

REFERENCES

- Hamady N.A., Abdel-Aziz H.A., Farog A.M. and Fakhr Issa M.A., *Monatshefte fur chemie.*, 138, 2007,1001-1010.
- Patel B.V., Patel H.S. and Patel K.C., *Ind. J. Chem.*,-B, 47B (06), 2008, 0376-4699.
- Ali T. El-sayad and Ibrahim M.A. *J.Braz. Chem.Soc.*, 446(2117), 2010, 1445-1468.
- Chan-Thaw C.E., Villa A., Katekonon P., Sus D., Thomas A. and Prate L., *Nano Lett.*, 10(2), 2010, 537-541.
- Kurumurthy C., Veeraswamy B. Rao P. S., Kumar G.S., Reddy V.L., Rao J.V. and Narsaiah B., *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry Lett.*, 24(3), 2014, 746-749.
- Sztanke K., Pasternak K., Rajtar B., Sztakne M., Majek M. and Polz-Dacewicz M.: *J.Bioorganic and Med.Chem.*,15, 2007, 5480-5486.
- Simanek E.E., Abdou H., Lalwani S., Lim J.J., Mintzer M., Venditto V.J. and Vittur B., *Proc. R. Soc. A*, 466(2117), 2003, 1445-1468.
- Krutz L.J., Shaner D.L., Weaver M.A., Webb R.M.T Zablutowicz R.M., Reddy K.N. Huang Y. and Thomson S.J., *Pest Management Sci.*, 66(5), 2010, 461-481.
- Lim J., Mintzer M.A., Perez L.M. and Simanek E.E., *Org.Lett.*, 12(6), 2010, 1148-1151.
- Mirano K., *Chem. Abstr.*, 79, 1973, 137200.
- Zhuo J., He C., Yao W., *United States, Patent Application Publication*, US2013/0345224 A1, 2013.
- Pittis W.J., Guo J., Dhar T.G., Shen Z., Gu H., Watterson S.H. and Bednarz M.S., *J.Bioorg.Med.Chem.*, 12(2), 1997.
- Hajiduk P.J., Dinges J., Schkeryantz J.M., Janowick D., Kaminski M., Tufano M., Augeri., *J.Med.Chem.*, 42, 1999, 3852-3859.
- Irikura T., Abe Y., Okamura K., Higo K., Maeda A., Morinaga F., Shirai G. And Hatae S., *J.Med.Chem.*, 13, 1970, 1081-1089.
- Bossinger C.D. and Tekeshi ., *Chem.Abstr.*, 77, 1972, 34590.
- Tani M., *Japan Patent*, 71(34), 1971, 429.
- Peultner F.E., *Chem.Abstr.*, 72, 1970, 111516.
- Gaigu A.G., *Siess Patent*, 393, 1965, 344.
- Toye, Kobtan Industries Ltd., *Chem.Abstr.*, 64, 1966, 35744.
- Cyril V. And Milan M., *Chem.Abstr.*, 86, 1977, 190015.
- Davis J., *U.S.Patent*, 4, 1980, 186, 265.
- Bitzer D., *Chem, Abstr.*, 93, 1980, 8217.
- Costeacho S., *Chem.Abstr.*, 93, 1980, 95301.
- Alfred K. And Tantaway A., *Chem. Abstr.*, 90, 1979, 54913.
- Jiang H., Deng X., Wang J., Wang J., Peng J., Zhou T., *PLoS ONE*, 9(4): e93654,doi.1013711/ Journal Pone 0093654, 2014.
- Jhala A.J., Sandell L.D., Rana N., Kruger G.R., and Khezevic S.Z *Weed Technology*, 28(1), 2014, 28-38.
- Helmut B., Willi K., Wolfgang K., Edger M., And Peter R., *Germ. Offen*, 2, 1978, 630/849; *Chem. Abstr.*, 88, 1978, 152668.

28. Berrer D. And Garade R., *Chem. Abstr.*, 92, 1980, 58833.
29. Wetwitayaklung P., Limmatvapirat C., Phaechamud T., *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Science* 756, 2013, 649-656.
30. Colthup N.B., Daly L.H., and Wiberley., "Introduction of IR and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, N.Y., p.279, 1964.
31. Tayade D.T., *Proc.*, 83rd *Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1996.
32. Silverstein R.M., Bassler G.C., And Morrill T.C "Spectroscopic Identification of Organic Compounds", 4th Ed., John Wiley and Sons, INC, N.Y. 1981.

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

